

The growing world population increases the pressure on the aquaculture sector. In addition to delivering **high-quality protein**, aquaculture production systems are also required to be **environmentally sustainable**, **ethical**, and with concerns for **animal welfare**.

From November 2022 to November 2026, **IGNITION will gather new knowledge on animal welfare under climate change scenarios and establish alternatives to the currently applied antimicrobials and therapeutic strategies.**

In line with the expected impacts of HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-06 call, IGNITION's outcomes will:

- Increase revenue and new business opportunities
- Increase value of feed products, enriched with bioactive compounds
- Reduce antimicrobial use and its related pollution and human health risks
- Improve circular economy
- Contribute to at least six of the **Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations**:

Coordinator

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IGNITION

IMPROVING GREEN INNOVATION FOR THE BLUE REVOLUTION

New tools and opportunities for a more sustainable animal farming

<https://ignition-project.eu/>

